

Design of a Six-Story Teaching Building: A Comprehensive Approach to Safety and Structural Efficiency

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Abstract:

This paper describes teaching building design. The project, designed for the teaching building, prioritizes safety in its main structure, a reinforced concrete frame with six floors above ground. The story heights are 4.2m, 3.9m, 3.9m, 3.9m, 3.9m and 3.9m, respectively, and the building's total height is 27.6m. The construction site category is classified as type II, and the first group's seismic fortification intensity is 7 degrees. The process includes architectural design, structural design, and PKPM checking calculation. Architectural design mainly consists of a general description. The plan, elevation, section, and draft of the corresponding building are drawn according to the relevant information and requirements provided by the design

task book. Structural design mainly includes load statistics, calculation of internal force and displacement of the frame, a combination of internal force, and calculation of staircase, slab roof, floor slab and frame structure. The calculation of displacement, internal force, and reinforcement of the whole frame structure is carried. Out using PKPM. In the course of architectural design, safety is a paramount consideration, in line with the principles of safety, applicability, beauty, economy, and energy-saving requirements, referring to national standards and relevant materials, and strictly following the requirements of relevant architectural design standards, the design of each link is not only a comprehensive scientific consideration of its own but also a related discussion with teachers, as detailed in the construction plan. The frame structure is adopted, in this structural type. It mainly includes structure layout and calculation sketch determination, load calculation, internal force calculation, internal force combination, main beam section design, and reinforcement calculation, frame column section design and reinforcement calculation, secondary beam section design and reinforcement calculation, floor and roof design, staircase design etc. Among them, the D-value method is used to calculate the internal force of the structure under horizontal load, and the distribution method is used to calculate the internal force of the structure under vertical load (dead load and live load).

Keywords: *Teaching building, Architecture design, Structural design, Frame structure, Moment distribution method, D value method.*

Introduction

"Modern architecture and building design have to follow an evolutionary path rather than a revolutionary one." Ieoh Ming Pei (Chinese-American architect). So, rather than focusing on a structure's aesthetics, we should focus on the foundation's construction (Lawson, & B. 2012). This design setup is a teaching building. It is for us to plan the use of data in the constructing arrangement, not just make each of us viewpoints consciously, and the adapting basically, that mastermind is very important (Annan, 2011). This design setting aims to create a sketch of the building site's thoroughfare (Shan, et al., 2019). During the task investigation, a man can also comprehend the building outline essential standards, fundamental strategies, and aptitudes, and based on this, choose a simple structure with building the general arranging, shape the rectangular style of compositional appearance (Pan, et al., 2018). Through the graduation plot, which anticipates that we will comprehend and master the entire method of teaching building design, develop our free examination limit and creative ability to deal with realistic issues, rehearse our examination and study, gather data and check data, and scrutinize remote written work limit, we will be able to resemble the draftsman's fundamental getting ready (Park, & Ang, 1985). Teaching building design code requirements, scheme design ability, structural design ability, drawing, and drawing skills are all important aspects of the design (Bayo, Mazzolani, & Bergman, 2006). These are the fundamental capabilities of architects. This topic will test our abilities in various ways, including translating specifications into drawings and project designs in the field. We will utilize Auto CAD and other software in this graduation project to design educational structures. The layout and vertical arrangement of the building are done using industry tools. Structural design is an important aspect of civil engineering since it deals with building and structures' structural strength and integrity (Gosain, Bertero, &

Hanson, 1997). A multi-layer frame structure is used in the design of the teaching building facility. A frame structure is a popular type of constructed structure. The main body is made up of beams and columns that are joined by rigid or hinged connections (Lacey, Wong, & Wu, 2018). The SATWE module in the Appendix (PKPM software calculation for overall analysis) will be used in the teaching building facility. Structural characteristics such as period and displacement ratio must all fulfill the specification criteria once the structural arrangement has been optimized (Zhang, Lu, & Yan, 2017). We must also utilize structural design to study the structural design of the building and the strength of different materials used to establish its safety and economic parameters as part of empirical research and analysis (Wight, 1981). The structural design guarantees the structure is robust enough to support the desired load and survive the elements. I will sort out and apply the existing knowledge in the design process. It is both an attempt and an exercise. This will cultivate oneself to establish correct design thinking, rigorous scientific attitude and work style, correctly master and apply design principles, and comprehensively consider all design aspects.

In the development process of civil engineering, practical engineering experience often precedes theory, and engineering accidents usually show unforeseen new factors, triggering the research and development of new theories. Public buildings are being built on a larger scale and in greater numbers than ever before, and they are becoming increasingly important in everyday life. In industrialized nations, the study of new contemporary teaching space is progressively becoming a field, and research on modern office space continues to appear in numerous specialized academic conferences, journals, and publications. Office buildings have become a symbol of the world's operational position in this century after architectural science has finished

the most prevalent signals of economic success, social advancement, and cardinal growth.

In the structural design aspect: The vertical load and level load casing structures are calculated individually, utilizing the contorting minute scattering process and the d-esteem strategy. (ii) After the casing has been resolved under various loads, each part's control region and most negative mix of inward powers must be identified (Pampanin, Priestley, & Sritharan, 2001). The regulation of the long-term burden impact by combining variable load with control. (iii) As shown in the adaptive hypothesis diagram, the second bar and plate plastic within the power redistribution system are "three levels, two stages" (Da Silva, & Vellasco, 2002). Appendix (PKPM software computation), software like AutoCAD are widely used in architectural and structural software applications in other countries. As a result, it is required to continually innovate and optimize the building characteristics to be developed, as well as to scientifically sort out and efficiently support the unique frame structure of the high-rise building. The building structure's reliability standard must meet the following functional requirements: the role that the frame structure can withstand during normal use, the structural components' good working performance during normal construction and use, and the structural components' durability under normal maintenance. When an emergency happens, the structural elements of the building can still preserve the structure's overall stability

Seismic design: When should we first make harm from the earthquake? (i) the outline of the "solid shear powerless twisting" solid shear frail

bowing flexibility is to guarantee that parts, to keep the weak disappointment of the vital standards, it requires falsely increment the bearing segment in respect to its capacity to oppose bowing shear bearing limit of these zones during the time spent structure encounter serious seismic tremor under adequate confirmation is definitely not a fragile sheer disappointment (Nguyen, & Le, 2013). It is important to focus on shear checking and development to meet the necessities of the solid edge structure shaft (Lui, & Chen, 1986). (iii) Complete the outline of the "solid hub feeble part" while building licenses, beyond what many would consider possible to do the segment estimate greater, make line firmness of segment and beamline solidness proportion as expansive as conceivable in 1 and control of hub pressure proportion meet the determination prerequisites, to expand the flexibility (Rodrigues, Silvestre, & de Oliveira, 2000).

Methodology

Architecture Design

Project Overview

This project is designing a teaching building based on concrete reinforcement. The general layout of the building is shown in Figure 1 below. The building structure is reinforced concrete with an area of about 8000m², a building height of 27.6m, 6 floors above the ground (main structure) and a floor height of 3.9m (4.2m on the first floor). The spacing between control axes is a multiple of 6.0m. And 3.6m.

Figure 1. Teaching Building Site Plan

Structure Total Information

The parameters required for the structural calculation of this project are given in Table 1.

Material Reinforcement: HRB400; Concrete: C30 or C40; Steel: Q235B or Q345B

Geological information: Foundation Profile is shown in Table 1-2.

Loads the calculation load is calculated according to Table 3 Calculation loads

Table 1. General information

Category and Criterion for Seismic Precaution	Standard Precautionary Category (Class C)
Seismic Precautionary intensity	Degree 7
Design basic acceleration of ground motion	0.1g
Construction Site Category	II类 Type II
Design Seismic Group	First group
Reference wind pressure	0.4kN/m ²
Reference snow pressure	0.65kN/m ²
Terrain roughness	B类 Class B

Table 2. Foundation Profile

Number	Type of soil	Depth of soil (m)	Thickness of soil (m)	Standard value for carrying capacity of soil f_k (kPa)
1	Miscellaneous Fill	0~1.2	1.2	—
2	Plastic Silty Clay	1.2~2.5	1.3	150
3	Hard Plastic Silty Clay	2.5~6.4	3.7	260
4	Strong Weathered rock	6.4~11.2	4.8	350

Table 1 Calculation loads

Load function zoning		Dead load on the floor	Floor live load
Floor load (kN/m ²)	Toilet	6.0	Load code for the design of building structures GB50009-2012
	Hall, corridor, classroom, auxiliary classroom	1.5	
	Stairs	2.0	

Graphic Design

The outline of the building is designed symmetrically in the shape of a Rectangle shape. The longitudinal axis distance is 76.5 m, and the transverse axis distance is 19.8 m. The longitudinal column distances are 6.0 m for the rooms and 3.6 m for the staircase, toilet, and photocopy Service Centre. The transverse column distances are 8.4m and 3.0m in this order. Number (left to right) has to be used for the X-axis lines, like 1, 2, 3, 4, 5..... The

alphabet (down to up) has to use a Y-axis line, like A, B, C, and D. The entrance door of 1st room adopts the national standard size, which is 3000 mm × 3200 mm, and the other side of the door size is 2400 mm × 3200 mm. The size of the door opening in rooms is 1200 mm × 2100 mm & 900×2100 double-open non-standard doors.

The first designs include the graphic design of the floor plan and first-floor plan, the standard floor plan of 2 to 5 floors and the 6th-floor plan:

Floor Plan 1:100

Figure 2. Floor Plan

First Floor Plan 1:100

Figure 3. First Floor Plan

2nd to 5rd Floor Plan 1:100

Figure 4. 2nd to 5th Floor Plan

Figure 5. 6th Floor Plan

Elevation Design

The building elevation is a drawing that helps the architect understand the facing of the building. The elevation facing includes the direction of the sunlight and wind. In addition, the building elevation design also consists of the height of the buildings as well as doors and windows. The elevation design is one of the earliest drawings

that are drawn early in the process of a project. In layman's terms, the building elevation is a visual picture of your upcoming home or remodeling project. It includes materials to be used, layout of space and rooms, and home decor. There are four types of building elevations. Such as: Front elevations, side elevations, rear elevations, and split elevations.

Figure 6. North Elevation

The building has six floors; one floor is 4.2m high, and each floor is 3.9 m. The indoor and outdoor height difference is taken as 0.45m. I selected three steps; the step height is 0.15m, so

the total building elevation is 28.05 m, measured from level -0.45m. The axis length of the south and North elevations is 76.5, and the axis length of the east and west elevations is 19.8m. The

arrangement of doors and windows should consider accessibility and safety and assess the specifications' requirements to achieve good daylighting and ventilation. The window height is 1.5m, and the north and south elevation windows are symmetrically arranged so that to achieve a harmonious and unified effect. The position is the same as that in the standard floor plan. On the south elevation, the stair's windowsills are 0.9m from the landing floor, the height of each window is 1.5m, and the height of the door at the entrance hall is 2.4 m. On the west elevation, the door at the entrance hall is 2.4m, and the outdoor window of the classroom is 2.1m. The South, north, west, and east elevations are shown in Figure 6.

Roof Drainage Design

Roof drainage has two main categories: Primary roof drains, Overflow, and secondary. Commonly referred to as an overflow system. The primary system consists of roof drains, piping serving those drains, and the discharge method used, which is surface or gravity drainage or pumped drainage. The gutter longitudinal slope is generally not less than 1%. In this design, the roof adopts a flat type roof, the drainage mode is organized single slope drainage, 8 PVC pipes with a diameter of 100mm are selected, and the roof slope is 2%. The layout of the roof drainage is shown in the figure below:

Figure 7. Roof Drainage Design

Results and Discussion

The chapter of results and discussion presents all data like as design calculation information of in situ roof, floor slab, staircase, and frame structure. Analysis of collected data to determine different parameters from different phases of the study which are also included in the test result by PKPM and AutoCAD Software.

Design Data of in Situ Roof Slab

Roof practice: 15mm slab bottom plastering (17kN/m³), 120mm cast-situ- reinforced

concrete roof slab (25kN/m³), 20mm hard cement mortar screed (20kN/m³), Waterproof layer and cement mortar protective layer 0.40kN / m².

Material used: Material used: Reinforcement: HRB400; Concrete: C30; Steel: Q235B or Q345B.

Standard Roof Structure Plan

The standard Roof structure is arranged as shown in the figure:

Figure 8. Roof Slab Design

According to the condition of cross-height ratio, the slab thickness should satisfy $h=3000/30 = 100\text{mm}$, so the roof slab thickness $h = 120\text{mm}$ is taken. (This is not a floor slab)

For secondary beams, $h = \text{span}*(1/18 \sim 1/12) = 8400*(1/18 \sim 1/12) = 467\text{mm} \sim 700\text{mm}$

Considering the large live load on the floor, $h = 500\text{mm}$ taken

$b = h*(1/2 \sim 1/3) = 600*(1/2 \sim 1/3) = 200 \sim 300\text{mm}$

$b = 200\text{mm}$ is set.

So, secondary beams $(b, h) = (200, 500)$

For determining dimensions of girders (main beams):

$h = \text{span}*(1/10 \sim 1/15) = 8400*(1/10 \sim 1/15) = 840\text{mm} \sim 560\text{mm}$, so take $h = 600\text{mm}$

$b = h*(1/2 \sim 1/3) = 800*(1/2 \sim 1/3) = 350\text{mm} \sim 233.333\text{mm}$, so take $h = 250\text{mm}$

So, determining dimensions of girders or main beam $= (b, h) = (250, 600)$

3.2 Design data of in situ floor slab

Floor slabs practice: 15mm slab bottom plastering (17kN/m³), 100mm cast-situ-reinforced concrete slab (25kN/m³), 20mm hard cement mortar screed (20kN/m³), ceramic floor tiles (0.35kN/m²).

Material used: Reinforcement: HRB400; Concrete: C30; Steel: Q235B or Q345B

Standard Floor Structure Plan

The standard floor structure is arranged as shown in the figure

Figure 9. Floor Slab Design

According to the condition of the cross-height ratio, the floor slab thickness is taken as $h=100\text{mm}$.

For secondary beams, $h = \text{span} \cdot (1/18 \sim 1/12) = 8400 \cdot (1/18 \sim 1/12) = 467\text{mm} \sim 700\text{mm}$

Considering the large live load on the floor, $h = 500\text{mm}$ taken

$b = h \cdot (1/2 \sim 1/3) = 600 \cdot (1/2 \sim 1/3) = 200 \sim 300\text{mm}$

$b = 200\text{mm}$ is set.

So, secondary beams $(b, h) = (200, 500)$

For determining dimensions of girders (main beams):

$h = \text{span} \cdot (1/10 \sim 1/15) = 8400 \cdot (1/10 \sim 1/15) = 840\text{mm} \sim 560\text{mm}$, so take $h = 600\text{mm}$

$b = h \cdot (1/2 \sim 1/3) = 800 \cdot (1/2 \sim 1/3) = 350\text{mm} \sim 233.333\text{mm}$, so take $h = 250\text{mm}$

so, determining dimensions of girders $= (b, h) = (250, 600)$

Design Data of Staircase

This design is for the inclined staircase in which there is use of cast in situ concrete for the slab.

The Floor height of all the floors from the second floor up to the six floors is exactly 3.9m

.First Floor height is 4.2m .depth of the stairs is 8.4m .width of the stairs is 3.6m .

Total Number of steps: $N = 26$

Tread: $b = 270\text{mm}$

Riser: $h = 3900/26 = 150\text{mm}$

Number of rise $= 3900/150 = 26$

Number of treads $= 26 - 1 = 25$

Calculate other parameters.

Length of the stairway $L = b [(N / 2) - 1] = 270[(26/2) - 1] = 3240\text{mm}$

Stairwell width is 3600mm , and the stairway width is: $a = (3600 - 250 - 240) / 2 = 1555\text{mm}$

Select the landing width: $D1 = D1' = 1750\text{mm} > a = 1555\text{mm}$ so fulfills the landing width requirements.

Choose the landing width: $D1 = 1750\text{mm} > a = 1555\text{mm}$

The above Calculated value of D meets the requirements of the landing width.

The Stairs used for study are between the axis 1 and 2 and the other sets of the axis are CD which is the depth of the staircase The staircase plan is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10. The Staircase Plan

The Design of stairway slab:

Use the equation $h = (1/30 \sim 1/25) \times l$ to determine the value of h which represents slab thickness of these stairs. The stairway slab thickness:

$$h = (1/30 \sim 1/25) \times 3240 = 108 \sim 130 \text{mm, choose } h=120 \text{mm.}$$

The following calculations are for finding the angle of inclination of the stairs.

$$\tan \alpha = h / b$$

$$= 150 / 270 = 0.56$$

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1}(150/270)$$

$$= 29.2^\circ$$

$\cos \alpha = 0.874$, therefore for the calculation, the following is the diagram which shows the angle

of inclination of then staircase and the loading for both live load and the dead load

Design Data of Frame

Basic wind pressure is 0.4kN/m^2 (Terrain roughness is Class B); Basic snow pressure is 0.65kN/m^2 ; Seismic fortification intensity is 7-degree, design basic acceleration of ground motion is $0.1g$, design earthquake group First group; Seismic fortification Category of buildings is category C; Category of construction site is category 2; the Service life of the structural design is 50 years. Engineering geology and geological conditions: the foundation of the building is silty clay, and its characteristic value of Foundation bearing capacity is 280kPa ; the standard freezing depth of the site is 0.8m ; the underground water level is 6.0m .

Figure 11. Frame Design

Materials utilized

Reinforcement : HRB400; Concrete : C30 or C40; Steel: Q235B or Q345B

A transverse frame calculation diagram

A Six-story office building is constructed by cast-in-situ reinforced concrete frame structure. This building is classified as standard protection

buildings (Category C). The strength grade of concrete which is employed for columns is C30, where $f_c=14.3\text{N/mm}^2$. And considering the seismic grade 1 of the frame structure. The total height of the building is 23.7m. The span length are as follows; $I_{AB}=I_{CD}=8400$, $I_{BC} =3000$.

The column height of the bottom layer is calculated from the top surface of the foundation to the second floor. The column height of the bottom storey is 5.2m. The column height of the second floor and the other floors is 3.9m. And then, we can obtain the calculation diagram of the calculation unit for transverse frame in axis of this Teaching building that is shown in following figure 11.

Defining the Sectional Dimensions of Columns

Estimating the sectional dimension for the column initially by using the following reference formula

$$A_c \geq \zeta N_v \mu / (f_c) \quad (1)$$

Here

$A_c \rightarrow$ the sectional area of a column.

$\zeta \rightarrow$ the amplifying coefficient, take 1.3~1.4.

$N_v \rightarrow$ the design value of axial load acting on the column, the standard value of vertical load take 12~15kN/m², and partial factor takes 1.25.

$\mu \rightarrow$ the limit value of axial compression ratio.

$f_c \rightarrow$ the axial compressive strength of concrete.

The strength grade of concrete which is employed for the column is C30, $f_c = 14.3 \text{ N/mm}^2$, and the axial compression ratio takes 0.65 according to the following Table 4.

Table 4. The Axial Compression Ratio

Structure type	Seismic grade			
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th
Frame structures	0.65	0.75	0.85	0.90
Frame-wall, slab-wall-Colum, tube structures.	0.75	0.85	0.90	0.95
Frame-support wall structures	0.60	0.70	-	-

And considering the seismic grade 1 of the frame structure according to the above table, the axial compression ratio takes 0.65

Loading Area of middle columns: $6(\text{Maximum Bay}) \times [(8.4+3)/2] = 34.2\text{m}^2$

Loading Area of the side columns: $6(\text{Maximum Bay}) \times (8.4/2) = 25.2 \text{ m}^2$

For middle columns:

$$A_c \geq 1.3 \times 12 \times 10^3 \times 6(\text{floors}) \times 34.2 / (0.65 \times 19.1) = 238008.86 \text{ mm}^2$$

For side columns:

$$A_c \geq 1.3 \times 12 \times 10^3 \times 6(\text{floors}) \times 25.2 / (0.65 \times 19.1) = 175374.95\text{mm}^2$$

According to the above calculation results and considering the structural requirements of the aforementioned frame columns, the cross-sectional dimensions of columns in this design are taken as follows: 600mm×600mm for 1-6story columns; the bottom columns take 600mm×600 mm.

Transverse frame beams: the transverse secondary beams are 200 mm X 500mm, and the main beams are 250mm X 600mm. When calculating the moment of inertia of the beam sections according to the sectional dimension of the beams. Considering the cast-in-situ floor slab, the exterior frame beams are taken as $I = 1.5I_0$ (the moment of inertia of the beam section without considering the effect of the slab); the interior take $I = 2.0I_0$. The floor slabs are cast-in-situ two-way slabs with a thickness of 100mm. which meets the requirements of the slab.

The Calculation of Internal Forces of Transverse Frame Structure under the Vertical Loads

Under vertical load, the calculation unit is axis 3. Within the calculation unit, the self-weight of the

longitudinal frame beams, longitudinal walls, and longitudinal parapets acts as a concentrated force on each joint.

Figure 12. Floor Plan of Axis 3 Vertical Load

Load Calculation of in Situ Roof, Floor Slab, Staircase, and Frame Structure

Load of Roof Slab Design

The standard value of permanent load:

15mm slab bottom plastering
 $0.015 \times 17 = 0.255 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

50mm polystyrene insulation layer
 $0.05 \times 0.5 = 0.025 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

120 mm cast-in-situ reinforced concrete slab
 $0.12 \times 25 = 3 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

30mm cement cinder leveling layer
 $0.03 \times 10 = 0.3 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

20mm cement mortar screed
 $0.02 \times 20 = 0.4 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

Waterproof layer and cement mortar protective layer
 $0.40 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

Total: $g_k = 4.38 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

The standard value of variable load:

In this design, the variable load on the roof slab is related to the roof live load and the roof snow load. A comparison shall be made and the larger

value shall be selected. This design adopts the unmanned roof, and the live load standard value is $0.5 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$. The value of snow load is based on the reference snow pressure within the 50-year mean recurrence interval snow pressure. According to the “Load Code for the Design of Building Structures GB 50009-2012”, the reference snow pressure in Nanjing city is $S_0 = 0.4 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$. I set the roof as an external horizontal roof, so $\mu_r = 1.0$. The standard value of roof snow load is calculated as follows: $S_K = \mu_r S_0 = 1.0 \times 0.4 = 0.4 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$. The result shows that the live load is greater than the snow load ($0.5 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2 > 0.4 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$), therefore, the standard value of variable load on the roof slab is taken as $0.5 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

Permanent load standard value: $g_k = 4.38 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

Variable load standard value: $q_k = 0.5 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

$1.35g_k + 0.7 \times 1.5q_k = 1.35 \times 4.38 + 0.7 \times 1.5 \times 0.5 = 6.44 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

$1.3g_k + 1.5q_k = 1.3 \times 3.88 + 1.5 \times 0.5 = 6.44 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$

So the permanent load controls the design, take $\gamma_g = 1.35$ and $\gamma_q = 1.5$

The design value of permanent load is: $g = 1.35 \times 4.38 = 5.91 \text{ kN/m}^2$

The design value of variable load is: $q = 1.5 \times 0.5 = 0.75 \text{ kN/m}^2$

The total design value of load is: $g+q = 5.91 + 0.75 = 6.66 \approx 7 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Calculation of the Slab

See the Table 5 below for the type of roof slabs

Table 5. The Type of Roof Slabs

One way slab	Two-way slab
B1-7	B2-1
B1-8	B2-2
B1-10	B2-3
B1-11	B2-4
	B2-5
	B2-6
	B2-9

Calculation of one-way slabs B1-7,

The ratios of the long span to the short span of B1-7 are $l_{02} / l_{01} = 6000 / 2675 = 2.24 > 2$, they are designed as one-way slabs.

End span of short span, $l_{01} = l_n = 2800 - 250 / 2 = 2675 \text{ mm}$

1m wide strip as the calculation unit. The calculation diagram is as shown in figure 13 below:

Figure 13. Calculation Diagram of B1-7

In this design, the slab and the beam are integrally connected. In the textbook "Concrete Structure volume II (Sixth Edition)" (China Construction Industry Press), the bending moment coefficients^a of each control section of the slab can be found from table 11-2. The coefficients are: End support A is -1/16; middle span 1 is 1/16. Therefore, the design value of the bending moment of each control section is:

$$M_A = -\frac{(g+q)l_{01}^2}{16} = -\frac{7 \times 2.675^2}{16} = -3.13 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

$$M_B = -\frac{(g+q)l_{01}^2}{11} = -\frac{7 \times 2.675^2}{11} = -4.55 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

$$M_1 = \frac{(g+q)l_{01}^2}{14} = \frac{7 \times 2.675^2}{14} = 3.58 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Calculation of flexural bearing capacity of normal section:

The environmental category is class I, strength grade of concrete is C30, the minimum concrete cover of slab is $c = 15 \text{ mm}$. Assuming that the longitudinal reinforcement diameter is $d = 10 \text{ mm}$ and the slab thickness $h = 100 \text{ mm}$, then the effective height of the section is $h_0 = h - c - d / 2 = 120 - 15 - 10 / 2 = 100 \text{ mm}$; the width of slab is $b = 1000 \text{ mm}$.

For C30 concrete grade, $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $f_c = 14.3 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_t = 1.43 \text{ N/mm}^2$ using HRB400 reinforcements, $f_y = 360 \text{ N/mm}^2$ the reinforcements of the slab are shown in the table below:

Table 6. Slab Reinforcement Calculation

Critical section	A	1	B
Moment ($kN \cdot m$)	- 3.13	3.58	- 4.55
$\alpha_s = M / \alpha_1 f_c b h_0^2$	0.022	0.025	0.032
$\delta = 1 - \sqrt{1 - 2\alpha_s}$	0.022 < 0.35	0.025 < 0.35	0.033 < 0.35
Calculated area of reinforcement (mm^2)	87.388	99.306	131.08

$A_s = \delta b h_o \alpha_1 f_c / f_y$			
Actual area of reinforcement(mm^2)	C 8@200 $A_s=251$	C 8@200 $A_s=251$	C 8@200 $A_s=251$

The calculation results show that δ of the support sections is far less than 0.35, so it conforms to the principle of redistribution of plastic internal force. However, the calculated reinforcement cross-sectional area is too small to meet the structural requirements, so structural reinforcement should be used in construction.

$\frac{A_s}{bh} = \frac{251}{1000 \times 100} = 0.25\%$ which is larger than $0.45 \frac{f_t}{f_y} = 0.45 \times \frac{1.43}{360} = 0.17\%$ and at the same time greater than 0.2%, which meets the requirements of the minimum reinforcement ratio.

Load calculation of staircase

Standard value of permanent load of stairway slab

Step floor ceramic tiles
 $(0.27+0.15) \times 0.35 / 0.27 = 0.54 kN/m^2$

Triangular step
 $0.56 \times (0.27 \times 0.15) \times 25 / 0.27 = 2.1 kN/m^2$

120mm cast-in-situ reinforced concrete slab
 $0.12 \times 25 / 0.874 = 3.43 kN/m^2$

20mm bottom plastering
 $0.02 \times 17 / 0.874 = 0.39 kN/m^2$

Total: $g_k = 6.46 kN/m^2$

Standard value of live load of stairway slab

According to the Load code, the standard value of uniformly distributed load on stairs is :

$q_k = 3.50 kN/m^2$

$1.35g_k + 0.7 \times 1.5q_k = 1.35 \times 6.46 + 0.7 \times 1.5 \times 3.50 = 12.40 kN/m^2$

$1.3g_k + 1.5q_k = 1.3 \times 6.46 + 1.5 \times 3.50 = 13.65 kN/m^2$

Therefore, the live load plays a controlling role.

Take $\gamma_g = 1.3$ and $\gamma_q = 1.5$

Taking 1m wide strip we have:

$q_k = 3.50 kN/m^2 \times 1m = 3.50 kN/m$

$g_k = 6.46 kN/m^2 \times 1m = 6.46 kN/m$

The design value of the total load of the stairway slab is:

$p = 1.3 \times 6.46 + 1.5 \times 3.5 = 13.65 kN/m$

The simplified calculation diagram is shown in figure 14 below:

Figure 14. Stairs Calculation Diagram

Cross-Section Design

The minimum concrete cover of slab is $c = 15mm$. Assuming that the longitudinal reinforcement diameter is $d = 10mm$. For C30 concrete grade. $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $f_c = \frac{14.3N}{mm^2}$, $f_t = 1.43N/mm^2$

, HRB400 reinforcements are used $f_y = 360N/mm^2$

The horizontal effective span of the stairway slab is: $l_n = 3240mm$, the design value of the mid-span bending moment is: $M = pl_n^2 / 10 = 13.65 \times 3.24^2 / 10 = 14.33 N/mm^2$

The effective height of the stairway slab is: $h_o = 120 - 20 = 100mm$

$\alpha_s = M / \alpha_1 f_c b h_o^2 = 14.33 \times 10^6 / 1.0 \times 14.3 \times 1000 \times 100^2 = 0.1002$

$$\delta = 1 - \sqrt{1 - 2\alpha_s} = 1 - \sqrt{1 - 2 \times 0.1002} = 0.1058$$

$$A_s = \delta b h_0 \alpha_1 f_c / f_y = 0.1058 \times 1000 \times 100 \times 1.0 \times 14.3 / 360 = 420 \text{ mm}^2$$

Select C12@200 for the longitudinal steel bars, and the actual area is $A_s = 565 \text{ mm}^2$. The short steel bars C 8@200 are arranged at the supports to resist negative bending moments, and the length of the steel bars is $l_n / 4 = 3240 / 4 = 810 \text{ mm}$. The horizontal reinforcement is a structural reinforcement, and C 12@200 reinforcement is optional.

Checking of the minimum reinforcement ratio:

The calculation results show that ξ is less than 0.35, so it conforms to the principle of redistribution of plastic internal force.

$$\frac{A_s}{bh} = \frac{479}{1000 \times 120} = 0.4\% \text{ which is larger than } 0.45 \frac{f_t}{f_y} = 0.45 \times \frac{1.43}{360} = 0.17\% \text{ which is larger than } 0.2\% \text{, which meets the requirements of the minimum reinforcement ratio. Use one distribution bar } 2A_{12} \text{ for each step.}$$

Design of landing slab

The thickness of the landing slab is the same as that of the stairway slab $h = 120 \text{ mm}$. The type of reinforcements and concrete grade used are the same as those of the stairway slab.

Load calculation:

Standard value of permanent load of landing slab

Floor ceramic tiles 0.35 kN/m^2

20mm cement mortar screed
 $0.02 \times 20 = 0.40 \text{ kN/m}^2$

120mm cast-in-situ reinforced concrete slab
 $0.12 \times 25 = 3.00 \text{ kN/m}^2$

15mm bottom plastering
 $0.015 \times 17 = 0.255 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Total: $g_k = 4.01 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Standard value of live load of landing slab

According to the Load code, the standard value of uniformly distributed load on the stairs is $q_k = 3.50 \text{ kN/m}^2$

$$1.35g_k + 0.7 \times 1.5q_k = 1.35 \times 4.01 + 0.7 \times 1.4 \times 3.50 = 8.64 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

$$1.3g_k + 1.5q_k = 1.3 \times 4.01 + 1.5 \times 3.50 = 10.46 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Therefore, the live load plays a controlling role.

Take $\gamma_g = 1.3$ and $\gamma_q = 1.5$

Taking 1m wide strip we have:

$$q_k = 3.50 \text{ kN/m}^2 \times 1 \text{ m} = 3.50 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$g_k = 4.01 \text{ kN/m}^2 \times 1 \text{ m} = 4.01 \text{ kN/m}$$

The design value of the total load of the landing slab is:

$$p = 1.3 \times 4.01 + 1.5 \times 3.5 = 10.46 \text{ kN/m}$$

13.4.1 Cross Section Design of landing slab

The thickness of the landing slab is the same as that of the stairway slab $h = 120 \text{ mm}$. The type of

The minimum concrete cover of slab is $c = 15 \text{ mm}$. Assuming that the longitudinal reinforcement diameter is $d = 10 \text{ mm}$. For C30 concrete grade:

$$\alpha_1 = 1.0, f_c = 14.3 \text{ N/mm}^2, f_t = 1.43 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

HRB400 reinforcements are used $f_y = 360 \text{ N/mm}^2$

The horizontal effective span of the landing slab is: $l_0 = 1750 - 125 = 1625 \text{ mm}$,

the design value of the mid-span bending moment is:

$$M = pl_n^2 / 10 = 10.46 \times 3.24^2 / 10 = 10.98 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

The effective height of the landing slab is: $h_0 = 120 - 20 = 100 \text{ mm}$

$$\alpha_s = M / \alpha_1 f_c b h_0^2 = 10.98 \times 10^6 / 1.0 \times 14.3 \times 1000 \times 100^2 = 0.077$$

$$\delta = 1 - \sqrt{1 - 2\alpha_s} = 1 - \sqrt{1 - 2 \times 0.077} = 0.0802$$

$$A_s = \delta b h_0 \alpha_1 f_c / f_y = 0.0802 \times 1000 \times 100 \times 1.0 \times 14.3 / 360 = 319 \text{ mm}^2$$

Select C10@200 for the longitudinal steel bars, and the actual area is $A_s = 392 \text{ mm}^2$. The short steel bars C8@200 are arranged at the supports to resist negative bending moments, and the length of the steel bars is $l_n / 4 = 1625 / 4 = 406.25 \text{ mm}$. The horizontal reinforcement is a structural reinforcement, and A8@200 reinforcement is optional.

Checking of the minimum reinforcement ratio:

The calculation results show that ξ is less than 0.35, so it conforms to the principle of redistribution of plastic internal force.

$$\frac{A_s}{bh} = \frac{393}{1000 \times 110} = 0.4\% \text{ which is larger than } 0.45 \frac{f_t}{f_y} = 0.45 \times \frac{1.43}{360} = 0.17\% \text{ which is larger than } 0.45 \frac{f_t}{f_y} = 0.45 \times \frac{1.43}{270} = 0.24\% \text{ and at the}$$

same time greater than 0.2%, which meets the requirements of the minimum reinforcement ratio

Design of landing beam

Assuming that the sectional dimension of the landing beam is 250mm x 300mm. Load calculation :

Standard value of permanent load of landing beam

$$\text{Landing beam self-weight } 0.25(0.30-0.10) \times 25 = 1.25 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$\text{Both sides and bottom plaster } 0.02 \times 17 [2(0.30-0.10) + 0.25] = 0.22 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$\text{Transmitted from landing slab } 3.51 \times [(1.750-0.125)/2] = 2.85 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$\text{Transmitted from waist slab } 6.46 \times 3.240 / 2 = 10.47 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$\text{Total: } g_k = 14.79 \text{ kN/m}$$

Standard value of live load of landing slab

$$q_k = 3.50(3.240/2 + 1.750/2) = 8.73 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$1.35g_k + 0.7 \times 1.5q_k = 1.35 \times 14.79 + 0.7 \times 1.5 \times 8.73 = 29.13 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$1.3g_k + 1.5q_k = 1.3 \times 14.79 + 1.5 \times 8.73 = 32.32 \text{ kN/m}$$

Therefore, the live load plays a controlling role.

Take $\gamma_g = 1.3$ and $\gamma_q = 1.5$. The design value of the total load of the waist slab is: $p = 1.3 \times 14.79 + 1.5 \times 8.73 = 32.32 \text{ kN/m}$

Cross section Design of landing beam

The minimum concrete cover of slab is $c = 15 \text{ mm}$. Assuming that the longitudinal reinforcement diameter is $d = 10 \text{ mm}$. For C30 concrete grade:

C30 concrete is selected for the column: For C30 concrete grade: $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $f_c = \frac{14.3 \text{ N}}{\text{mm}^2}$, $f_t = 1.43 \text{ N/mm}^2$

HRB400 steel for longitudinal reinforcement and stirrups: $f_y = 360 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $f_{yv} = 360 \text{ N/mm}^2$

The effective span of the landing beam is: $l_0 = 1.05l_n = 1.05(3.6-0.25) = 3.52 \text{ m}$.

The design value of the mid-span bending moment is:

$$M = Pl_0^2 / 8 = 32.32 \times 3.52^2 / 8 = 50.06 \text{ kNm}$$

The design value of shear force is:

$$V = Pl_0 / 2 = 32.32 \times 3.52 / 2 = 56.88 \text{ kN/m}$$

The section is designed as a T-section:

$$b'_f = b + 5h'_f = 250 + 5 \times 100 = 750 \text{ mm}$$

The effective height of the landing beam is: $h_0 = 300 - 20 - 10 - 10 / 2 = 265 \text{ mm}$

• Calculation of the beam bearing capacity of normal section:

$$M_u = \alpha_1 f_c h_f (h_0 - 0.5h'_f) = 1.0 \times 14.3 \times 750 \times 100 (265 - 0.5 \times 100) = 230$$

$M_u > M = 50.06 \text{ kN.m}$, therefore it belongs to the type 1 of T-section.

$$\alpha_s = M/\alpha_1 f_c b h_0^2 = 50.06 \times 10^6 / 1.0 \times 14.3 \times 750 \times 100^2 = 0.467$$

$$\delta = 1 - \sqrt{1 - 2\alpha_s} = 1 - \sqrt{1 - 2 \times 0.467} = 0.743$$

$$A_s = \delta b h_0 \alpha_1 f_c /$$

$$f_y = 0.743 \times 750 \times 100 \times 1.0 \times 14.3 / 360 = 2213 \text{ mm}^2$$

Calculation of the bearing capacity of the inclined section:

According to the design process of the secondary beam, the stirrups are set as C 8@200

for both legs according to the structural requirements and the shear capacity of the inclined section is checked:

$$V_{CS} = 0.7 f_t b h_0 + f_{yv} A_{sv} h_0 / s$$

$$= 0.7 \times 1.43 \times 250 \times 265 + 360 \times 57 \times 265 / 200$$

$$= 935 \text{ kN/m} > 56.88 \text{ kN/m}$$

The section meets the requirements.

Load of Frame Design

(1) The distributed linear load acting on the beam of the 6th floor

I. Calculating of dead load:

Exterior beams:

The dead load transmitted from roof $4.0 \times 3.6 = 14.4 \text{ kN/m}$

Self - weight of transverse beam $0.29 \times 0.6 \times 25 = 4.35 \text{ kN/m}$

Add up to $= 18.75 \text{ kN/m}$

Corridor beams:

The dead load transmitted from roof $4.0 \times 3.6 = 14.4 \text{ kN/m}$

Self - weight of transverse beam $0.29 \times 0.6 \times 25 = 4.35 \text{ kN/m}$

Add up to $= 18.75 \text{ kN/m}$

2. Calculating of live load: $2.0 \times 3.6 = 7.20 \text{ kN/m}$

2. The distributed linear load acting on the beam of 5th -1st floor

I. Calculating of dead load:

Exterior beams:

The dead load transmitted from floor $1.5 \times 3.6 = 5.4 \text{ kN/m}$

Self - weight of transverse beam $0.29 \times 0.6 \times 25 = 4.35 \text{ kN/m}$

Self - weight of interior transverse wall $0.82 \times (3.9 - 0.6) = 2.71 \text{ kN/m}$

Add up to $= 12.46 \text{ kN/m}$

Corridor beams:

The dead load transmitted from floor $1.5 \times 3.6 = 5.4 \text{ kN/m}$

Self - weight of transverse beam $0.29 \times 0.6 \times 25 = 4.35 \text{ kN/m}$

Add up to $= 9.75 \text{ kN/m}$

Figure 15. The Calculating of Loads

Calculating on Internal Forces of Vertical Load

The frame's internal force under vertical load is determined using the moment distribution technique. The undesirable arrangement of live load may be overlooked in normal industrial and civil structures, with the exception of industrial facilities with substantial live load. The bending moment at the mid-span of the beam produced using this approach is less than that obtained using the disadvantageous live load arrangement. When the section is strengthened, the mid-span bending moment can be modified by doubling the amplification factor of 1.1~ 1.2

The whole frame may be employed in calculations since the transverse frame structure and load are symmetrical. The shear force at the beam end may be calculated by superposing the shear force generated by the vertical load on the beam and the shear force induced by the bending moment at the beam end after calculating the bending moment at the ends of the beam and column. By superimposing the shear force at the beam end and the concentrated load at the joint, the axial force of the column may be calculated.

Bending moments at fixed ends are calculated. To compute the bending moment at fixed ends, the frame beam is treated as a beam that is fixed at both ends, as illustrated in Table.

Table 7. Calculating on the Bending Moments at the Fixed Ends of Frame Beam

Side span			Intermediate span		
Distributed load/kN.m ⁻¹	l/m	M=(ql ² /12)/kN.m	Distributed load/kN.m ⁻¹	l/m	M=(ql ² /12)/kN.m
18.75	8.4	110.25	18.75	3.0	14.06
12.46	8.4	73.26	9.75	3.0	7.31
7.20	8.4	42.34	7.20	3.0	5.4

The partition coefficient is being calculated. Because the internal forces are computed using the entire frame, the cut beam's line stiffness is double that of the original, and the allocation coefficient is determined using the ratio of the angel stiffness of each component connecting to the joint. Figure 16 depicts the linear stiffness of the beam and column in the whole frame.

Figure 16. Diagram of Linear Stiffness of Full-Frame Beam and Column

The allocation coefficient of point 1:

Right beam- i_{b1} & Upper column- i_{c1} are 0

Left beam- i_{b2}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x32143}{4x0+4x32143+4x0+4x83077} = 0.279$$

Lower column- i_{c2}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{c2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x0+4x32143+4x0+4x83077} = 0.721$$

The allocation coefficient of point 2

Right beam- i_{b1}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b1}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x32143}{4x32143+4x90000+4x0+4x83077} = 0.016$$

Left beam- i_{b2}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x90000}{4x32143+4x90000+4x0+4x83077} = 0.439$$

Upper column- $i_{c1} = 0$

Lower column- i_{c2}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x32143+4x90000+4x0+4x83077} = 0.405$$

The allocation coefficient of point 3,5,7&9

Right beam- $i_{b1} = 0$

Left beam- i_{b2}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x32143}{4x0+4x32143+4x83077+4x83077} = 0.162$$

Upper column- i_{c1}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c1}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x0+4x32143+4x83077+4x83077} = 0.419$$

Lower column- i_{c2}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x0+4x32143+4x83077+4x83077} = 0.419$$

The allocation coefficient of point 4, 6, 8&10

Right beam- i_{b1}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b1}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x32143}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x83077} = 0.111$$

Left beam- i_{b2}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x90000}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x83077} = 0.312$$

Upper column- i_{c1}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c1}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x83077} = 0.288$$

Lower column- i_{c2}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x83077} = 0.288$$

The allocation coefficient of point 11:

Right beam- $i_{b1} = 0$

Left beam- i_{b2}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x32143}{4x0+4x32143+4x83077+4x62308} = 0.181$$

Upper column- i_{c1}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c1}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x0+4x32143+4x83077+4x62308} = 0.468$$

Lower column- i_{c2}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x62308}{4x0+4x32143+4x83077+4x62308} = 0.351$$

The allocation coefficient of point 12

Right beam- i_{b1}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b1}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x32143}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x62308} = 0.120$$

Left beam- i_{b2}

$$\mu_{\text{beam}} = \frac{i_{b2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x90000}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x62308} = 0.336$$

Upper column- i_{c1}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c1}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{4x83077}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x62308} = 0.311$$

Lower column- i_{c2}

$$\mu_{\text{column}} = \frac{i_{c2}}{4i_{b1}+4i_{b2}+i_{c1}+4i_{c2}} = \frac{62308}{4x32143+4x90000+4x83077+4x62308} = 0.23$$

Figure 17. Diagram of Bending Moment Distribution for Dead Load (KN·m)

Figure 18. Diagram of Bending Moment Distribution for Live Load (kN·m)

(3) Coefficient of transfer While the distal end is fixed, the transfer coefficient is 1/2. When the distal end is sliding hinged, the transfer coefficient is -1.

(4) Using the moment distribution to calculate. Figure 17 depicts the frame's bending moment

distribution calculation under dead load, whereas Figure 19 depicts the frame's bending moment diagram. The frame's bending moment distribution calculation under live load is given in Fig. 18, and the frame's bending moment diagram is displayed in Fig. 20.

Take the moment modulation coefficient of 0.8 to account for the redistribution of plastic internal force at the ends of frame beams under vertical load. The bending moments of the dead and live loads are presented in bracketed values in Fig.9.6 and Fig.9.7 after amplitude modulation.

The Maximum span moment M_{max}

While the vertical loads, dead load and live load are combined, span moment M_{max} can be

approximately replaced by the bending moment at mid-span, i.e.

$$M \approx ql^2/8 - (M_{left} + M_{right})/2$$

Where M_{left} and M_{right} are the left -end moment and right- end moment of beam respectively, the values of them are in parenthesis in fig and fig .if the mid-span moment is less than the value of $ql^2/8$, $M = ql^2/8$ should be taken , q is the dead load or live load

Figure 19. The Bending Moment Diagram of the Plane Frame under Dead Load

Figure 20. The Bending Moment Diagram of the Plane Frame under Live Load

(5) Calculating on shear force at beam end and axial force on column

Shear force at beam end: $V_{Left} = V_{qleft} + V_{m,left}$

$V_{Left} = V_{qleft} + V_{m,right}$

Axial force on column: $V_{right} = V_i + P_i + N_{i+1} + W_i$

Diagram for calculating of N

Where ,shear force is calculated by taking the method of isolating body according to structural

mechanics, with denoting clockwise angle around the bar as positive and counterclockwise angle as negative. The bending moment at the beam end is positive clockwise and negative counterclockwise.

V_{qleft} V_{qlight} =The shear force of left and right end of beam with simply supports:
 $V_{qlight} = -V_{m,right} = 0.5ql$

V_{qlight} V_{qright} =The sheer force caused by bending moment of beam ends

$$V_{mleft} = -V_{m,right} = -(M_{lft} + M_{right})/l$$

V_i =The total shears of beam ends in number i floor:

p_i =The concentrated load acting on the joint in number i floor;

N_{i+1} =The axial force at the bottom of column which is in number i+1;

w_i = Self-weight of the column in number i floor, only for the bottom section of the column.

The calculation process is illustrated by taking the exterior columns in top two stories of the side span under dead load

Table 9. The Beam End Shears and Column Axial Force under Dead Load (KN)

Floors	Total shears				Axial force of column			
	Exterior spans(AB)		Interior spans(BC)		Exterior column(A)		Interior column(B)	
	V_{left}	V_{right}	V_{left}	V_{right}	N_{top}	N_{bottom}	N_{top}	N_{bottom}
6	74.04	-83.46	28.13	-28.13	113.46	153.40	99.12	139.06
5	52.35	-52.32	14.63	-14.63	254.20	294.13	232.34	272.28
4	52.00	-52.66	14.63	-14.63	394.59	434.53	365.90	405.84
3	52.00	-52.66	14.63	-14.63	534.98	574.92	499.46	539.40
2	51.95	-52.72	14.63	-14.63	675.32	751.26	633.08	673.02
1	51.74	-52.92	14.63	-14.63	815.45	868.70	766.90	820.15

Table 10. The Beam End Shears and Column Axial Force under Live Load (KN)

Floors	Total shears				Axial force of column			
	Exterior spans(AB)		Interior spans(BC)		Exterior column(A)		Interior column(B)	
	V_{left}	V_{right}	V_{left}	V_{right}	N_{top}	N_{bottom}	N_{top}	N_{bottom}
6	28.54	-31.94	10.80	-10.80	67.96	107.90	47.60	87.54
5	30.13	-30.35	10.80	-10.80	186.47	226.41	158.85	198.79
4	30.03	-30.45	10.80	-10.80	304.89	344.83	270.20	310.14
3	30.03	-30.45	10.80	-10.80	423.31	463.25	381.55	421.49
2	30.00	-30.48	10.80	-10.80	541.71	581.65	492.93	532.87
1	29.7	-30.61	10.80	-10.80	659.97	713.22	604.44	657.69

Conclusion

Building design education is discussed in this study. Safety is given first priority in the project's primary structure, a reinforced concrete frame with six stories above ground, which is intended for the teaching building . The major components of structural design include load statistics, internal force and displacement of the frame calculations, internal force combinations, and calculations for the floor slab, staircase, slab roof, and frame structure. With PKPM, the displacement, internal force, and reinforcement

of the entire frame structure are calculated. Safety is the most important factor when designing an architectural structure. This is done in accordance with the principles of safety, applicability, beauty, economy, and energy-saving requirements; national standards and pertinent materials are consulted; and the relevant architectural design standards are strictly adhered to; each link's design is not only a thorough scientific consideration on its own but also a discussion with teachers about the subject, as indicated in the construction plan. For this structural type, the frame structure is

used. Included are the following: main beam section design and reinforcement calculation; frame column section design and reinforcement calculation; floor and roof design; staircase design; foundation design; load calculation; internal force calculation; internal force combination; and so on. Among them, the internal force of the structure under a horizontal load is determined using the D-value method, and the internal force under a vertical load (i.e., a dead load and a live load) is determined using the distribution method.

Author Contributions

MITHUN BISWAS investigation, funding acquisition, and writing – original draft preparation writing; Prodhon Md Safiq Raiha: original draft preparation, data analysis, writing, review and editing, and checking the original draft; PRODHAN MD ATOWAR RAHMAN: writing – review and editing and checking the original draft; S M CHAYAN: investigation, funding acquisition, checking the original draft, and writing, review and editing; Anik Md Shahjahan: checking the original draft and data analysis. All authors have accepted responsibility for the entire content of this manuscript and approved its submission.

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